

Correlates of Punctuality and Teamwork as Teachers' Ethical Practices for Effective Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

Asila, Joy Eyaal & Dr. Godfrey Nnadiye
Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt

Abstract

This study investigated the correlates of punctuality and teamwork as teachers' ethical practices for effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The total population of the study was 138 school administrators, consisting of 54 school administrators from Port Harcourt City Local Government Area and 84 school administrators from Obio-Akpor Local Government Area from the 46 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The population was manageable; therefore, the researcher used the entire population as the sample adopting census sampling technique. The instruments for the study were two different self-structured questionnaires titled: "Teachers' Ethical Practices Questionnaire" and "Effective Job Performance Questionnaire" which were on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The instruments were face and content validated by three experts, one from the Department of Educational Management and two from Measurement and Evaluation respectively all in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded cumulative reliability indexes of 0.82 and 0.84 for the two instruments respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics was used in answering the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using t-Transformation at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that a high positive and significant relationship exist between teachers' punctuality and teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school leadership should strictly monitor and enforce punctuality as a non-negotiable standard by rewarding punctual teachers and sanctioning habitual lateness so as to enhance effective utilization of instructional time.

Keywords: Punctuality, Teamwork, Ethical, Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are the backbone of an educational activity. The success and failure of educational activities highly depend on their performance. Their performance is directly linked to process and product of education. Therefore, the performance of teachers is emphatic for the improvement of education. Performance may be described as "an act of accomplishing or executing a given task". It could also be described as the ability to combine skillfully the right behaviour towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives (Olaniyan, 2019). Performance incorporates the resulting outcomes of the performed actions of employees based on their expertise and skills. Consequently, teacher performance is how a member of teaching staff fulfils the duties of their role, completes required tasks and behaves in the school workplace.

It is a sign of the capacity of an individual teacher in a workplace to efficiently achieve independent goals. In most organizational settings, employees' performance is the accumulation of skills, efforts and abilities of all the employees to contribute in organization for improved productivity leading towards its goal achievement.

Improved organizational performance indicates the efforts towards goal achievement while requiring more efforts in terms of improved employee performance (Ellinger, Ellinger & Keller, 2017). According to Karakas (2020), the term "teacher performance" signifies individual teacher work achievement after exerting required effort on the job which is associated through getting a meaningful work, engaged profile, and compassionate colleagues/employers around.

Ethics is a branch of philosophy that deals with the theory of value. In the school system, ethics is a set of moral principles and values that govern individual teachers, which they are bound to observe. Ethical practices of teachers are behaviours expected of a classroom teacher to exhibit which will not contravene the lay down rules and regulations governing the teaching profession. Adegboye and Oyekan (2022), defined teachers' ethical practices to encompass adherence to professional standards, integrity, respect for students' rights and commitment to moral values that foster a conducive learning environment. In the same vein, Umeh and Nwankwo (2024), asserted that ethical

practices in the teaching profession involve maintaining professionalism, fairness, honesty and confidentiality while dealing with students, colleagues and parents. Teachers who exhibit high ethical standards are more likely to be committed, diligent and effective in their teaching roles, which can significantly improve students' learning experiences (Eze, 2023).

On the contrary, a lack of ethical behaviour among teachers can result in negative outcomes, such as poor academic performance, increased dropout rates and diminished public trust in the education system (Nwachukwu, 2024). Within the teaching profession, ethical practices include but not limited to: punctuality, dressing decently, right communication, respect, team work, confidentiality, empathy, fairness, accountability, responsibility for educational programmes and non-corruption (Oparaji, Ugwu & Chime, 2021). However, where there is professional laxity on the part of the teachers, there will be signs of absenteeism, favoritism, abuse of authority, persistent lateness to school, irregular and unauthorized movement from duty post and indiscipline among others which affects teachers' ability to perform their duties effectively (Adebayo, 2023). Teachers Code of Conduct in Igwe (2015), noted that teachers' ethical practices encompass integrity, punctuality, accountability, empathy, fairness, role model, team work etcetera. When teachers uphold these ethical principles, they promote a conducive learning environment that fosters students' academic success and overall job performance (Adebayo & Ibe, 2024).

Teachers' punctuality refers to the consistent habit of being on time in fulfilling their professional duties, including arriving at school, attending classes and submitting tasks within specified timelines. Teachers who demonstrate punctuality contribute to the smooth operation of school activities, improve students' time management skills, and reduce disruptions in the learning process (Gupta & Aggarwal, 2019). Punctuality reflects a teacher's commitment to professionalism and responsibility, which are essential for maintaining the credibility of the teaching profession. When teachers arrive on time, they set the tone for an organized and structured learning experience, ensuring that lessons commence as scheduled and instructional time is maximized. Research indicates that teachers' punctuality correlates with student engagement and academic achievement, as students are more likely to respect and emulate teachers who consistently adhere to time-bound schedules (Adeyemi & Adu, 2019). Punctuality also enhances teachers' ability to complete the curriculum effectively. In secondary schools, where subjects are often time-bound within tight schedules, late arrival disrupts lesson plans, reducing the time available for instructional delivery (Wink, LaRusso & Smith, 2021).

Studies have shown that teachers who maintain punctuality experience less stress related to curriculum coverage and student assessment because they systematically manage their responsibilities (Ololube, 2021). Furthermore, teachers who are consistently on time can conduct lesson preparations more effectively, ensuring that they are well-equipped with teaching materials, thereby enhancing the quality of instruction.

Teachers' punctuality as an ethical practice significantly enhances their job performance in secondary schools by fostering a disciplined learning environment, improving instructional effectiveness, and serving as a model for students. Malabo (2017), stated that punctuality of teachers to class enable them in the completion of scheme of work, but teachers who are not punctual end up rushing through their lesson delivery and also find it difficult entertaining questions from students in the areas they find confusing. Ultimately this rush of lesson robs the learners of quality learning because the teachers are bereft of quality lesson delivery. Igwe (2015), maintained that unpunctuality of teachers to school makes teachers to scramble for time or rush their lessons near examination time in an attempt to complete scheme of work or syllabus to compensate for time irretrievably lost. When teachers frequently come late to school or absent, they deprive the learners the opportunity of experiencing full explanation of concepts. If the students are fortunate to have a particular lesson repeated, it might be an abbreviated version of the original lesson and at the expense of the later lessons, since the teacher at this time will be in a hurry to cover up the syllabus so as to meet up with time. This situation according to Gluchmana and Gluchmanováb (2016), results in under achievement of students which may also lead to an increase in drop-out rate; thereby affecting negatively, parents' zeal to spend more money sending their children to school. Therefore, the punctuality rates by teachers to school can either lead to poor or improved academic performance of students.

Punctuality of teachers is an important life skill for the school system, as it is not uncommon for teachers to be sent home or fired from work for showing up late always. The punctuality of teachers to school and class takes the academic performance of students to a higher pedestal (Herminingsih, Anik & Widenti, 2017). Some teachers go to the classroom 40 minutes to 50 minutes late for a 1½ hour lesson. Obilor (2019), buttressed that as a result of lack of punctuality, such teachers rush through their lessons to cover up for lost time which impacts negatively on students' comprehension of the taught content and material leading to poor academic performance. On the other hand, teachers that are punctual to duty have enough time to complete their lesson, answer students' questions and attend to slow

learners, the result of which is improved performance. Darwin, Sherly, Edy and Acai (2019), revealed that teachers who are punctual to class and school activities often achieve more than those who are not. As a result of regular attendance to the class, the teacher avoids rushing through the lessons to cover up for lost time, by so doing slower learners will be able to grasp the concepts and will not lag behind (Musili, 2015). Teachers who are always regular to school can instill such attitude in pupils and this can result to good academic performance of the students (Molokomphale & Mavis, 2017).

Teachers' punctuality strengthens teacher-student relationships by fostering trust and mutual respect. When teachers are punctual, students perceive them as reliable and committed, which enhances classroom discipline and student participation. Teachers who model punctuality encourage students to adopt similar habits, which contribute to overall school discipline and improved academic performance. Moreover, school administrators are more likely to recognize and reward punctual teachers, leading to increased job satisfaction and motivation, which further boosts their job performance (Nwankwo & Uche, 2022). From a broader perspective, punctuality contributes to a positive school culture, where all stakeholders, including students, parents, and colleagues, view the institution as well-managed and professional. Teachers who adhere to punctuality policies demonstrate ethical leadership, influencing their peers to adopt similar attitudes. According to a study by Ofoegbu (2020), schools with strict adherence to punctuality report higher levels of teacher productivity and reduced absenteeism, as teachers feel a sense of accountability towards their roles. This, in turn, leads to better student outcomes and enhances the reputation of the school. Within the teaching profession, rules of ethics include but not limited to punctuality to school and lesson. Sanger and Osguthorge (2018), submitted that teachers' punctuality is the attitudinal expression of his continued interest in his job. This means that a teacher that comes late to school or even goes late to class for lesson is passing a simple message to school authority that he is done with the job.

Teachers' teamwork refers to the collaborative efforts of teachers to achieve common goals in the teaching and learning process by sharing responsibilities, ideas and resources. It involves working together to plan lessons, solve problems, and improve students' learning outcomes through mutual support and cooperation (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2018). Vangrieken, Dochy, Raes and Kyndt (2015), stated that effective teamwork among teachers enhances professional growth, encourages knowledge sharing and fosters a sense of community

within the school environment. Similarly, Kelchtermans (2016), opined that teachers' teamwork improves job satisfaction, reduces burnout, and leads to better decision-making and classroom practices. By collaborating with colleagues, teachers can address diverse learning needs, promote innovation and improve overall school performance (Senge, Cambron-McCabe, Lucas, Smith & Dutton, 2015).

Teachers' teamwork plays a critical role in enhancing job performance in secondary schools by fostering collaboration, shared expertise, and a supportive work environment. When teachers work together, they create a collective intelligence that helps address instructional challenges, improve student outcomes, and promote professional growth. Effective teamwork enhances lesson planning, classroom management, and the overall efficiency of the teaching and learning process. According to Johnson, Johnson and Smith (2020), teamwork among teachers leads to increased job satisfaction and reduces burnout, as educators feel more supported and less isolated in handling academic and administrative responsibilities. By sharing best practices, teachers refine their instructional strategies, making them more effective in delivering the curriculum. Furthermore, a collaborative work culture encourages mentorship, where experienced teachers guide less experienced colleagues, enhancing their professional competencies and confidence in executing their duties.

Another significant aspect of teamwork among teachers is the promotion of interdisciplinary teaching and curriculum integration. When teachers from different subject areas work together, they can create cross-disciplinary lessons that enrich students' understanding and make learning more engaging. For instance, a Civic Education teacher collaborating with a History or Government teacher can develop a holistic perspective on democratic principles and governance, thereby deepening students' comprehension. As suggested by Hargreaves and O'Connor (2018), teamwork in schools fosters innovation, as teachers brainstorm and experiment with new teaching methodologies. This process of continuous improvement ultimately benefits students and increases teachers' effectiveness. Additionally, when teachers collaborate in professional learning communities, they engage in data-driven decision-making, analyzing student performance to adjust teaching methods and interventions for better learning outcomes (DuFour & DuFour, 2018). Such initiatives ensure that instructional practices are evidence-based and aligned with students' needs. A collaborative environment reduces workplace conflict, promotes mutual respect, and enhances morale. When teachers work as a team, they can collectively address behavioural challenges among students, enforce school policies consistently, and create a safe and conducive learning environment. According to DuFour and Eaker

(2019), school culture significantly impacts teacher effectiveness, and schools that prioritize teamwork experience higher levels of engagement and commitment among teachers. Additionally, team collaboration extends to administrative duties, such as organizing school events, mentoring student clubs, and participating in decision-making processes. These activities contribute to teachers' holistic job performance, as they become actively involved in shaping the school's academic and extracurricular landscape.

Encouraging teamwork aid teachers to do meaningful work together so as to improve professional interaction, productivity and instruction. Williams (2019), stated that collaboration builds self-efficacy by allowing teachers to exert competency of their professional lives. Effective teacher team work allows teachers to reflect on their instructional practices and become more confident in their professional abilities. Consistent collaboration on professional practices results in reflective thinking, improved instructional strategies and student achievement. Thus, team work helps build trusting relationships and promotes a positive learning environment, and a positive learning environment has a positive influence on student achievement. When teachers work collaboratively with each other, they share experiences and innovative strategies; during collaborative discussions, teachers are given a voice in curricular implementation and variety of skills to support student learning needs.

Teachers' teamwork enhances the exchange of knowledge, relevant questioning and mutual accountability among teachers, which result in effective learning opportunities driven by student data (Bryk, Gomez, Grunow & LeMahieu, 2015). Redding (2019), suggested that school administrators (principals) are essential in establishing a teamwork culture among teachers. School teachers, in turn, model how to prioritize teamwork and actively engage in this behaviour. Principals are influential in engaging teachers' professional knowledge through teamwork. Thus, school principals should work cooperatively with teachers to encourage teachers' teamwork as this is a prerequisite for improving the quality of instructional delivery. When teamwork is encouraged, teachers' knowledge and experience are diffused and instruction is enhanced. Teachers with various levels of experience that collectively focus on improving student learning are most effective in increasing instructional delivery when teamwork is encouraged (Urick, 2016). When teachers have opportunities to collaborate professionally, they build upon their distinctive experiences, pedagogies and content (Goddard & Goddard, 2015). Ponder in Mulyadi (2015), concluded that teachers who work on teams report a greater skill variety and knowledge of student

performance, which, in turn, improves their job performance.

Teamwork amongst teachers can be formal or informal. For instance, inclusion requires general education teachers to work collaboratively with special education teachers to provide specified learning accommodations for students with disabilities. Some departmentalized teachers work on teams to integrate the curriculum for students. Many schools have also developed support teams for teachers to identify and address students' learning needs. Teachers' teamwork can even be demonstrated when teachers are discussing lesson strategies or student's needs during planning time. Many opportunities are available for teacher collaboration; yet, it is one of the least researched areas within the education field. Teachers' teamwork is a systematic process that allows teachers to analyze and improve instructional practices and student learning outcomes collaboratively with their fellow teachers (Williams, 2019). Teamwork among teachers serves as a means to improve instructional practices and students' achievement by shifting the focus from individual teaching to collective learning and understanding of concepts, thereby ensuring better student comprehension (Adebayo, 2023). Through teamwork, teachers can learn from each other, ask relevant questions, and hold one another accountable for their teaching activities, leveraging student data to provide effective learning opportunities (Goddard & Goddard, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

Despite these guidelines, some teachers exhibit unethical practices that negatively impact students' academic performance and overall school outcomes (Eze, 2020). These unethical practices and behaviours range from fraud, sexual abuse, abuse of office, using vulgar languages on students, extortion, harassment of students, unlawful punishment of students, examination malpractice and indecent dressing. Consequently, these unethical practices tend to lead students into more confusion in schools as much of the teaching and learning time is not used to achieve secondary education goals. Accordingly, it is not clear if a relationship exists between ethical practices and effective job performance. Hence the study examined relationship between teachers' ethical practices and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between teachers' ethical practices and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. examine the relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State;
2. determine the relationship between teachers' teamwork and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' teamwork and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' teamwork and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted correlational research design. This research design was considered appropriate for this study because it established the relationship between teachers' ethical practices and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The population of this study was one hundred and thirty-eight (138) Principals including Vice

Principal (Administration) and Vice Principal (Academic) from the forty-six (46) public senior secondary schools in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt City Local Government Areas of Rivers State (Port Harcourt City Local Government Area = 18; while Obio/Akpor Local Government Area = 28). The population was manageable, therefore, the researcher adopted census sampling meaning that the entire population was engaged in the study. Two questionnaires titled: "Teachers' Ethical Practices Questionnaire (TEPQ)" and "Effective Job Performance Questionnaire (EJPQ)" were used as instruments for data collection in this study. The instruments were structured on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points; Agree (A) = 3 points; Disagree (D) = 2 points; and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point respectively. The instruments were subjected to face and content validity by three experts, one (1) from Educational Management and two experts of Measurement and Evaluation from Educational Foundations, respectively, in Rivers State University. The reliability of the instruments were established using Cronbach Alpha method which gave cumulative reliability indexes of 0.82 and 0.84 for the two instruments respectively.

The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) or (r). The relationship of 0.1 - 0.4 was counted as "low correlation", 0.5 denoted "moderate correlation" while 0.6 - 0.9 denoted "high correlation". The null hypotheses were tested using t-Transformation at 0.05 level of significance with a critical t-value of 1.96. When the t-Transformation value is less than the t-critical value of 1.96, the null hypothesis was accepted and rejected when the t-Transformed value is greater than the t-critical value of 1.96.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Teachers' Punctuality and Effective Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

		Correlations**		
		Teachers' Punctuality	Effective Job Performance	Level of Correlation
Teachers' Punctuality	Pearson Correlation	1	.793**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	138	138	High and
Effective Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	.793**	1	Positive
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		Relationship
	N	138	138	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researchers' SPSS Statistical Output (2025).

Table 1 above for Research Question 4 showed the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result on Table 1 revealed that responses to questionnaire items 1-7 for teachers' punctuality and questionnaire items 1-7 for effective job performance had a correlation value of .793**. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between

teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. This result implies that teachers' punctuality leads to improved effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Teachers' Team Work and Effective Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

		Correlations**		
		Teachers' Team Work	Effective Job Performance	Level of Correlation
Teachers' Team Work	Pearson Correlation	1	.828**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	138	138	High and Positive Relationship
Effective Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	.828**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	138	138	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researchers' SPSS Statistical Output (2025).

Table 2 above for Research Question 5 showed the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result on Table 2 revealed that responses to questionnaire items 8-14 for teachers' team work and questionnaire items 1-7 for effective job performance had a correlation value of .828**. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt

Metropolis of Rivers State. This result implies that teachers' team work leads to improved effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Hypotheses

Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of t-Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Punctuality and Effective Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-Trans.	α	t-crit.	Decision
Teachers' Punctuality	138			15.18			Ho ₁ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
		136	.793		0.05	1.96	
Effective Job Performance	138						

Source: Research's t-Transformation Analysis (2025).

Data on Table 1 above showed a t-Transformation value of 15.18 and a t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 136. These values are also in conformity with Table 1, where the P-value is less than the significant level [P=.000 < (0.05)].

The t-Transformation value of 15.18 was greater than the t-critical value of 1.96, since the t-transformation value is greater than the critical value or the P-value less than the significance level, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' punctuality

and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State was rejected and the alternative upheld. In other words, there is a significant relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. This implies that teachers with high punctuality are likely to be more effective in job

performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 2: Summary of t-Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Team Work and Effective Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-Trans.	α	t-crit.	Decision
Teachers' Team Work	138						
		136	.828	17.22	0.05	1.96	Ho ₅ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
Effective Job Performance	138						

Source: Research's t-Transformation Analysis (2025).

Data on Table 2 above showed a t-Transformation value of 17.22 and a t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 136. These values are also in conformity with Table 2, where the P-value is less than the significant level [$P=.000 < (0.05)$]. The t-Transformation value of 17.22 was greater than the t-critical value of 1.96, since the t-transformation value is greater than the critical value or the P-value less than the significance level, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State was rejected and the alternative upheld. In other words, there is a significant relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. This implies that teachers' with high team work are likely to be effective in job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Relationship Between Teachers' Punctuality and Effective Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

The findings obtained on Research Question 1 in Table 1 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State with 'r' as .793**. The finding is in line with Molokomphale and Mavis (2017), who stated that teachers who are always regular to school can instill such attitude in pupils and this can result to good academic performance of the students. Hypothesis 1 in Table 3 showed that there is a significant relationship between teachers' punctuality and effective

job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State with t-Transformation value of 15.18 which was greater than the t-critical value of 1.96. The finding was supported by Malabo (2017), who stated that punctuality of teachers to class enable them in the completion of scheme of work, but teachers who are not punctual end up rushing through their lesson delivery and also find it difficult entertaining questions from students in the areas they find confusing.

Relationship Between Teachers' Team Work and Effective Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

The findings obtained on Research Question 2 in Table 2 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State with 'r' as .828**. The finding is in line with Vangrieken, Dochy, Raes and Kyndt (2015), who stated that effective teamwork among teachers enhances professional growth, encourages knowledge sharing and fosters a sense of community within the school environment.

Hypothesis 4 in Table 4 showed that there is a significant relationship between teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State with t-Transformation value of 17.22 which was greater than the t-critical value of 1.96. The finding corroborates with Williams (2019), who stated that collaboration builds self-efficacy by allowing teachers to exert competency of their professional lives. Effective teacher team work allows teachers to reflect on their instructional practices and become more confident in their professional abilities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that a high positive and significant relationship exist between teachers' punctuality and teachers' team work and effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Teachers need to constantly reflect on the ethics of their activities to ensure that they exhibit the best ethical practices possible in discharging their duties.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

1. School leadership should strictly monitor and enforce punctuality as a non-negotiable standard by rewarding punctual teachers and sanctioning habitual lateness so as to enhance effective utilization of instructional time.
2. School administrators should strengthen collaborative structures such as subject committees, team teaching, and inter-departmental meetings so as to build a culture of teamwork.

References

- Adebayo, K. (2023). Ethical challenges in Nigeria's educational sector: Implications for policy. *Journal of Educational Leadership, 15*(2), 45-60.
- Adeyemi, T.O., & Adu, E. T. (2019). Time management and teacher effectiveness in secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Management, 33*(3), 45-60.
- Bryk, A. S., Gomez, L. M., Grunow, A., & LeMahieu, P. G. (2015). *Learning to improve: How America's schools can get better at getting better*. Harvard Education Press.
- Darwin L., Sherly, Edy, D. & Acai, S. (2019). The Impact of work discipline and work ethic on the teacher performance of sultan agung pematangsiantar private middle school teachers T.A. 2018/2019. *International Journal of Business Studies, 3*(3), 125-135.
- DuFour, R. & DuFour, R. (2018). *The school leader's guide to professional learning communities at work*. Solution Tree Press.
- Gluchmana, V. & Gluchmanová, M. (2016). Ethical relationships in the teaching profession in Slovakia. *Journal of Educational Sciences and Psychology, 6*(68), 1-20.
- Goddard, Y. L. & Goddard, R. D. (2015). A theoretical and empirical investigation of teacher collaboration for school improvement and student achievement in public elementary schools. *Teacher College Record, 109*(4), 877-896.
- Gupta, P. & Aggarwal, R. (2019). Time management in education: Teachers' punctuality as a catalyst for student success. *Journal of Educational Leadership, 12*(3), 120-134.
- Hargreaves, A. & Fullan, M. (2013). *Professional capital: Transforming teaching in every school*. London. Teachers College Press.
- Herminingsih, A. & Widenti, S. (2017). The effect of work ethics, transformational and transactional leadership on work performance of teachers. *Management Studies, 5*(3), 250-261.
- Igwe, L. E. B. (2015). *Work ethics: Implication for performance indices*. Paper presented at the Annual Teachers' Workshop of Brainfield Group of Schools, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.
- Johnson, B., Johnson, D. W. & Smith, K. (2020). Cooperative learning: Improving university instruction by basing practice on validated theory. *Journal of Excellence in College Teaching, 31*(4), 83-112.
- Karakas, F. (2020). Spirituality and performance in organizations: A literature review. *Journal of Business Ethics, 94*(1), 89-106.
- Kelchtermans, G. (2016). Teacher collaboration and its impact on professional identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 22*(6), 613-625.
- Malabo, B. (2017) *Factors affecting academic performance of grant-aided and non – grant aided secondary schools: A Case of selected secondary schools in the Western Province of Zambia*. A Master of Education Thesis: University of Zambia
- Molokomphele, L. & Mavis, B. M. (2014). Investigation on students' academic performance for junior secondary schools in Botswana. *European Journal of Educational Research, 3*(1), 111-127
- Mulyadi, D. (2015). *Kepemimpinan dan Perilaku Organisasi Cetakan Ketiga*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Nwachukwu, I. (2024). Ethical misconduct in Nigerian schools: Causes and consequences. *Educational Management Review, 18*(4), 234-256.
- Nwankwo, O. & Uche, R. (2022). Professional ethics and teacher effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools. *African Journal of Education and Development Studies, 14*(1), 67-85.

- Obilor, E. I. (2019). Teacher factors influencing students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Academy Journal of Educational Technology and Research*, 7(2): 28-41
- Ofoegbu, F. (2020). School climate and teacher productivity: The role of ethical leadership. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, 12(2), 112-129.
- Olaniyan, A. O. (2019). *Principal preparation, selection and leadership roles" teachers and teaching in Nigeria*. Benin, Nigeria: Festa Press Ltd.
- Ololube, N.P. (2021). Teachers' job performance and time utilization: A study of public secondary schools. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 16(5), 78-91.
- Oparaji, I. C., Ugwu, I. & Chime, G. (2021). Teaching ethics as determinants of teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Okigwe education zone, Imo State, *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 3(3), 275-281.
- Redding, C. (2019). A teacher like me: A review of the effect of student-teacher racial/ethnic matching on teacher perceptions of students and student academic and behavioural outcomes. *Review of educational research*, 89(4), 499-535.
- Sanger, M. & Osguthorpe, R. (2018). *The moral work of teaching and teacher education. Preparing and supporting practitioners*. New York: Teachers College Press
- Ofoegbu, F. (2020). School climate and teacher productivity: The role of ethical leadership. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, 12(2), 112-129.
- Senge, P. M., Cambron-McCabe, N., Lucas, T., Smith, B. & Dutton, J. (2015). *Schools that learn: A fifth discipline field book for educators, parents and everyone who cares about education*. London. Crown Business.
- Urick, A. (2016). The influence of typologies of school leaders on teacher retention: A multilevel latent class analysis. *Journal of educational administration*, 54(4), 434-468.
- Vangrieken, K., Dochy, F., Raes, E. & Kyndt, E. (2015). Teacher collaboration: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 15, 17-40.
- Williams, M. L. (2019). *Teacher Collaboration as Professional Development in a Large, Suburban High School*. Dissertation, University of Nebraska.
- Wink, M. N., LaRusso, M. D. & Smith, R. L. (2021). Teacher empathy and students with problem behaviours: examining teachers' perceptions, responses, relationships, and burnout. *Psychological School*, 58, 1575-1596.